

FOURIER TRANSFORM FOR NON-UNIFORMLY SAMPLED DATA IN THE STUDY OF SYSTEMATIC ERRORS IN COMMON-VIEW TIME TRANSFER

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Abstract

A new mathematical formulation for the Fourier transform applicable to non-uniformly sampled data has been derived. The importance of this to the Global Positioning System (GPS) is identification of harmonics of the orbital period in the frequency of both the space vehicle and the ground reference clocks relative to the DoD Master Clock. The presence of such a periodicity was discovered in doing the exhaustive computation of frequency stability, *i.e.*, in estimating the stability at sample times equal to every multiple of the basic sample period of the data as opposed to the common method of under-sampling the stability at a canonic set of sample times equally spaced along a logarithmic axis. Analysis of the frequency stability of the time reference at the Air Force GPS ground tracking station at Colorado Springs showed a pronounced periodic component at 2.99 hours—the fourth harmonic of the operational GPS space vehicle orbital period of 11.97 hours.

Background

Analysis of the frequency stability of the ground reference clocks at the monitor stations and of the space vehicle clocks of the Global Positioning System is performed by the Naval Research Laboratory¹ using pseudorange observations of the Navstar space vehicles by the monitor stations and the post-processed precise ephemerides produced by the National Imagery and Mapping Agency (NIMA). The observations are synchronized to GPS time and are made every 15 minutes. Synchronization of the measurements enables the offset of the ground reference clocks from the DoD Master Clock to be obtained by Linked Common-View Time Transfer (LCVTT) [1] from the Washington, D.C. monitor station. The data would appear to be uniformly sampled except for missing measurements due to a number of causes such as communication outages, monitor station initialization, and switching of ground reference clocks. The exhaustive calculation of frequency stability, *i.e.*, for sample times equal to every multiple of the 15-minute sample period, has revealed for very stable clocks periodic components

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not visible using the common method of under-sampling the stability profile. For example, in *Figure 1* the Allan deviation for the offset of the time reference at the Colorado Springs monitor station—Alternate Master Clock #1 (AMC #1)—from the DoD Master Clock at the U.S. Naval Observatory (USNO) shows strong periodicities at approximately one day and at approximately three hours.

FREQUENCY STABILITY OF COLORADO SPRINGS TIME REFERENCE FROM
WASHINGTON, D.C. TIME REFERENCE VIA
COMMON-VIEW TIME TRANSFER
1-SEP-97 to 1-JAN-98

Figure 1

Efforts to apply spectral analysis to the data were initially frustrated by the requirement of the Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) and its Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) implementation that the data be uniformly sampled. The problem was overcome by deriving a new algorithm not subject to this restriction. The new formulation was derived by approximating the Fourier integral of the continuous offset of the two clocks by the Riemann sum defined by successive non-uniform samples of the continuous offset. This method has the following advantages: (1) While the Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) and its Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) implementation require that the data be uniformly sampled, the new transform may be applied to non-uniformly sampled data. (2) While the FFT is an N to N mapping where N is 2^m , the new transform is an N to M mapping where N (number of data points) and M (number of spectral estimates) are arbitrary integers. (3) While the classical FFT yields spectral estimates for frequencies from 0 to f_n where f_n is the Nyquist frequency equal to half the sampling rate, the range of frequencies over which spectral estimates can now be computed is completely

arbitrary. And, (4) since the frequencies at which the spectrum is estimated are independent of the length of the sample, the lengths of the samples whose spectra are to be averaged may be chosen arbitrarily—restricted only by the resolution required in the analysis. Departure from the FFT sacrifices economy in the computations, but with the vastly increased speed and memory of present-day computers such economy may only be necessary in real-time applications or in those cases where extremely long data records are encountered.

Non-Uniformity

In addition to missing measurements, the non-uniformity in the sample intervals that must be dealt with may arise from limitations of the receiver, from the measurement schedule, from computer roundoff error in representing the measurement time, or from the vagaries of the algorithm processing the data. While a careful analysis of the data may suggest ways to minimize the non-uniformity in future data collection and processing, spectral analysis must often be applied to data already corrupted by the collection and handling process.

For example, the 15-minute observations of the pseudorange of a Navstar space vehicle by a monitor station and the precise ephemeris provided by NIMA are time-tagged by year, day, hour, and minute. The phase offset of the space vehicle clock from the ground reference clock at the monitor station as computed from the pseudorange and the precise ephemeris is stored in formatted records where the time expressed as a modified

Figure 2

Julian date was formatted to five decimal places. The resulting Linked Common-View Time Transfer from the NIMA Washington, D.C. monitor station to the other GPS monitor stations suffers from the same limitation. The effect of the resulting roundoff can be seen in Figure 2 where the nominal 15-minute sample period of the offset of the Colorado Springs time reference from the DoD

Master Clock in Washington, D.C. alternates between 14.9904 and 15.0048 minutes. Also in evidence are short periods of missing measurements. A similar error appears to affect the 13-minute data collected by USNO as shown in Figure 3 where the nominal 13-minute sample period alternates between 12.9888 and 13.0032 minutes.

Figure 3

Another source of error appears to affect the data in Figure 4 where, in addition to roundoff error, there are a substantial number of sample intervals around 12.6 minutes in duration. While the mean sample interval of

Figure 4

the nominal one-day measurements of phase offset of the Navstar 15 cesium clock from the DoD Master Clock at USNO can be seen from Figure 5 to be close to a sidereal day of 1436 minutes, there is considerable scatter to the intervals. Finally, in Figure 6 is shown the error in the nominal one-day sample intervals resulting from the algorithm that processes the 15-minute measurements from the Ascension Island monitor station. Again the mean sample interval is close to a sidereal day of 1436 minutes, but the sample intervals suffer considerable scatter. If each pass of 15-minute measurements were interpolated at the time of closest approach (TCA) of the space vehicle, one would expect a uniform sample interval. Judging from

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the distribution of sample intervals, the interpolation was done at the measurement time closest to TCA.

Figure 5

Figure 6

Derivation

The transform used here is a generalization of the discrete transform and was derived heuristically based on the *shah*, or sampling function, described by Bracewell [2]. The derivation proceeds as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 G(f) &= \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \text{shah}\left(\frac{t}{\Delta_n}\right) g(t) w(t) e^{-i2\pi f t} dt \\
 &= \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \Delta_n \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} \delta\left(t - \frac{n}{\Delta_n}\right) g(t) w(t) e^{-i2\pi f t} dt \\
 &= \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \Delta_n \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} \delta(t - t_n) g(t) w(t) e^{-i2\pi f t} dt \\
 &= \sum_{n=1}^{N-1} \Delta_n g(t_n) w(t_n) e^{-i2\pi f t_n}
 \end{aligned}$$

where the Δ_n are just the spacings $|t_{n+1} - t_n|$ of the individual δ functions in the sequence represented by the *shah* function. The integrand in the first line of the derivation states that the continuous process $g(t)$ may be thought of as being sampled by the infinite sequence of δ functions, represented by *shah*(t / Δ_n), at the irregular times t_n and both truncated to some finite observation interval of N samples and weighted by the data window $w(t)$. In the second and third lines of the derivation the *shah* function is expanded and scaled. In the fourth line of the development the sifting property of the δ function yields the finite sum (limited by the duration of the data window $w(t)$) of the integrand evaluated at the irregular times t_n . The upper limit of the sum is restricted to $N-1$ by the definition of the n th time interval Δ_n .

Another argument leading to the same result proceeds as follows. Consider a continuous process $g(t)$ truncated to a finite interval and weighted over that interval by the data window $w(t)$. We wish to evaluate the Fourier integral of this finite extent of the continuous process. Because of the necessity of evaluating the integral on a digital computer, we must turn to one of the many techniques of numerical integration, e.g., Davis and Rabinowitz [3]. The simplest of these rules is to expand the integral as a Riemann sum of inscribed or circumscribed rectangles using as the points of division the irregular sampling times. There are more accurate rules for numerical integration, but the more sophisticated methods require manipulation (some adaptive to the behavior of the data) of the sampling times during the integration. The *a priori* assignment of sampling times places rather severe constraints on the methods available. Some improvement over the Riemann sum could be realized by generalizing the trapezoidal rule to the case of irregular sampling times. Extending the rule to such a case can be shown to lead to the following:

$$\begin{aligned}
 G(f) &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=1}^{N-1} \Delta_n \left[g(t_n) w(t_n) e^{-i2\pi f t_n} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + g(t_{n+1}) w(t_{n+1}) e^{-i2\pi f t_{n+1}} \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

Notice that the frequency f is continuous since we are dealing with an aperiodic function. Since there are few restrictions on the frequency f except for that imposed by the Nyquist criterion, *i.e.*, that a low-pass process should be sampled at a rate which is twice the highest frequency component of the process in order to avoid aliasing, we are free to evaluate the transform at any set of frequencies. Indeed, if we wish, we could evaluate the transform over a band of frequencies as opposed to the entire range of frequencies as normally required by the FFT. Or, we might wish to be clever and make the algorithm adaptive by clustering more frequencies near the peaks in the spectrum where the slope is rapidly changing in order to more accurately render the spectrum. In practice, however, because a number of sample spectra are usually

averaged to improve the stability of the spectral estimates, the spectrum is sampled uniformly over the same range for each data sample.

For the case of non-uniform sampling, the relationship between the Nyquist criterion and the sampling rate needs clarification. Shannon [4] remarked that the number of samples required to reconstitute a sampled function need not be equally spaced. Beutler [5] later proved this "folk theorem", *i.e.*, that a signal may be represented by any linear combination of irregularly spaced samples provided that the average sample rate exceeds the Nyquist rate. Hence, for non-uniform sampling the sample rate used to compute the Nyquist rate is interpreted to be the average sample rate and not the basic sample rate of the process.

Validation

To validate the new formulation of the Fourier transform, the new algorithm was applied to simulated data. The simulated data was uniformly sampled and consisted of 1000 measurements with a sample interval of 15 minutes, white noise at a level of $2 \text{ pp}10^{14}$ at a sample time of one day, and a three-hour sinusoid at a level of $5 \text{ pp}10^{13}$. Cosine fourth weighting with 92 db sidelobes was used to weight the single data sample. The result of transforming this one sample of data is presented in *Figure 7* which shows the three-hour sinusoid centered at 8 cycles per day.

Figure 7

Application

Spectral analysis using the new algorithm was applied to the data that was used to generate the stability profile in *Figure 1*. The 15-minute average frequency offset of the Colorado Springs time reference (AMC #1) from the DoD Master Clock is shown in *Figure 8*. One large gap in the data on 22 October can be easily seen. On a more expanded scale, such as that used in *Figure 2*, a large

number of smaller gaps would be visible as they are in that figure. The transform was applied to the frequency offset

Figure 8

in lieu of the phase offset because the many low-frequency trends in the phase would swamp the smaller systematic effects being examined. The 122-day span of data from 1 September 1997 to 1 January 1998 was divided into 12 equal samples 10.17 days in length. This choice of sample length placed the large gap in the data at the edge of a sample where its influence would be suppressed by the cosine fourth weighting of the data. This was done strictly as a matter of convenience since there is no requirement that the samples be of equal length. One thousand spectral estimates were computed equally spaced between 0 and 10 cycles per day for each data sample and the sample spectra averaged to yield the spectrum in *Figure 9*. A strong spectral peak occurs at

Figure 9

slightly more than eight cycles per day or, more precisely, at 2.99 hours corresponding to the fourth harmonic of the orbital period of 11.97 hours.

Because this strong spectral component is a harmonic of the orbital period, it was initially thought that it may have resulted from residual error in the post-fit ephemeris since, in common-view time transfer, the space vehicle clock should cancel out. But an error in the orbit in an asymmetrical common-view situation would not cancel. However, an error in the ephemeris would be expected to affect the computed range to the space vehicle from all of the monitor stations. In comparing the stability profiles for each of the monitor stations, it was noted that only Colorado Springs and those stations linked to it showed the three-hour systematic which argues against an error in the ephemeris large enough to cause the observed effect. In place of the Linked Common-View Time Transfer previously used, time was transferred from Washington, D.C. directly to Hawaii by common-view thereby bypassing Colorado Springs. The spectrum for the common-view time transfer in *Figure 10* shows no spectral component near eight cycles per day. Time transfer by

SPECTRUM OF HAWAII FREQUENCY OFFSET FROM
WASHINGTON, D.C. TIME REFERENCE VIA
COMMON-VIEW TIME TRANSFER
1-SEP-97 TO 1-JAN-98

Figure 10

common view was also performed from Hawaii to Kwajalein Island which had shown the three-hour cycle in the Linked Common-View Time Transfer from Washington through Colorado Springs. Again, there was no evidence of the three-hour cycle in the spectrum.

From this, it appears that the three-hour periodicity in the behavior of the time transfer from Washington to Colorado is peculiar to Colorado and must be caused by something at that monitor station. The periodicity appears to be independent of the time reference since it was seen in 1995 when the time reference was a single HP5071 cesium clock and again now that the time reference is the Alternate Master Clock. Another source of error could be the coordinates of the GPS antenna at the monitor station which are unique to that station. Hence, if the coordinates were in error, the computed range to the space vehicle would be in error, the computed phase offset of the space vehicle clock from the monitor station ground reference clock would be in error, and the space vehicle clock would

not cancel in the common-view time transfer. This suggests a thorough check of the accuracy of the Colorado Springs coordinates and the possibility of experimentally adjusting the coordinates in the software that processes the observations and the precise ephemeris to see if the three-hour cycle can be eliminated.

Conclusions

A new algorithm for the Fourier transform has been derived which is applicable to non-uniformly sampled time series. The algorithm was validated using simulated white noise with an embedded sinusoid. This new formulation will provide the capability to perform spectral analysis on data sets that have measurements missing or measurements taken at non-uniform sample times.

The new algorithm has been applied to the spectral analysis of the time transfer from the DoD Master Clock to the ground reference clocks at the other monitor stations. The results suggest that the source of the three-hour periodicity in the stability profile of the Colorado Springs time reference might be error in the station coordinates in the software used to derive the phase offset from the monitor station observations and the precise ephemeris—a possibility that will be assessed by further research.

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